

EARTH SCIENCES

PHENOGENETIC ANALYSIS OF THE POPULATION DYNAMICS OF CRAYFISH *ASTACUS ASTACUS* L. AFTER INTRODUCTION INTO A NATURAL RESERVOIR

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Abstract

This article presents an overview of the colonization dynamics of crayfish in a reservoir, specifically focusing on Lake Berezno in the Pskov region. The study involved trapping crayfish (*Astacus astacus*) as representatives of the overall population. To ensure accuracy, certain factors were considered, such as the season of catching, standard fishing gear, bait used, comprehensive morphometric analysis of individuals, and the sex ratio in the population. Based on the data collected in 1998, significant changes were observed in the ecological and genetic state of the crayfish population in Lake Berezno. These changes were possibly influenced by the implementation of a new morphogenetic program aimed at developing the entire useful territory of the lake. Interestingly, the crayfish population did not exhibit size polymorphism, and there was a single morphotype with a Gaussian size distribution. The variation in size observed in the crayfish population is attributed to the trapping methods used, as indicated by the asymmetry and kurtosis of variation. Remarkably, the noble crayfish *A. astacus* follows similar ecological and genetic patterns observed in other studied aquatic animals. This suggests that crayfish can serve as a reliable biological indicator to assess the state of the aquatic ecosystem.

Keywords: Noble crayfish *Astacus astacus*, bioindication, population, phenogenetic analysis, Verhulst-Gause, *Zygogramma suturalis*.

Crayfish are organisms that supply valuable food products, and their natural reserves in Western Europe and northwestern Russia have decreased due to anthropogenic impact on the environment [1–3]. Rational nature management in this direction is based on the creation of specialized farms - crayfish farms and the introduction of a small exact herd of mature crayfish into a new reservoir for the subsequent increase in the population [2, 4]. Noble crayfish *Astacus astacus* L are important not only as a source of delicious food [4, 5]. They are a biological indicator of the quality of the aquatic environment [7]. The article attempts to study and model an important ecological process - the development of a new reservoir by crayfish. Both a theoretical model of the process and a linkage of the model to the real situation studied by the authors in Lake Berezno (Gdovsky district of the Pskov region) are given.

General dynamics of population

The laws of developing a free ecological niche were studied by G. Gause [8]. The population growth curve in most cases (sometimes called the Verhulst-Gause curve) has the form shown in Fig. 1. Models of Gause, with their perfection, had flaws. The last stage of development of the ecological niche by organisms has been little studied. Gause worked on laboratory populations of ciliates, where there were rigid boundaries of the ecological niche (flask walls) and a finite number of resources. In nature, the boundaries of ecological niches are usually blurred, and the possibilities for obtaining food resources remain even when the main sources are exhausted.

Fig. 1. Verhulst-Gause curve in general form. 1 - stable population, search for ways to adapt. 2 - exponential growth, 3 - population stabilization, 4 - population decline, 5 - transition to a stable minimum abundance.

In this regard, the work [9] proposes a modification of the Verhulst-Gause curve (Fig. 2). A curve can have several mathematical descriptions, for example in terms of a hyperbolic tangent:

$$N = th(At^2 + Bt + C) + C$$

The disadvantage of the classical Gause model is the lack of consideration of the oscillatory processes occurring in any ecological system. The classical models of Gause and other ecologists [8] did not take into account the genetic characteristics of the population. In particular, the models ignored the concept of biological variability and considered the population as a collection of identical elements - individuals, which is not true.

When describing the process of colonization of a reservoir, it is advisable to use models developed for other invertebrates, with the introduction of coefficients that reflect the specific ecology of crayfish. For example, the distribution dynamics of the zygogram beetle (*Zygogramma suturalis*) was studied in the Stavropol Territory, where it was introduced for biological control of the quarantine weed ragweed [10]. A new phenomenon was described - a solitary population wave, i.e. the movement of organisms in a single dense front during the development of an ecological niche. We can assume the existence of similar processes in the development of new niches by crustaceans.

Fig. 2. Spread of crayfish from the primary zone of settlement. The circle shows the possible dynamics of settlement in a homogeneous environment, the shaded areas show the actual settlement within the coastal strip.

For a wave to occur, the population must be over-consolidated in the area of the initial population. At the periphery of the range, an arc wave occurs, where the density of the population is increased, and from its borders, the resettlement of animals is ensured over the entire area suitable for habitation. Figure 2 shows a diagram of the formation of an annular solitary wave in the settlement model. At the same time, the territory inhabited by organisms does not grow exponentially (as in the Gauze model), but quadratically with time - at a constant speed of movement, the radius of the circle grows linearly with time, and the area, respectively, depending on the second power of time.

This is described by the formula:

$$N = Kt^2,$$

K is a constant coefficient. This moment corresponds to the stage of transition from exponential dependence to linear growth.

Principles of phenogenetic indication in the construction of settlement models

The analysis of these processes by methods of population genetics makes it possible to determine the previous and future fate of the population. The phenogenetic method is based on the results of a one-time analysis of the population [11]. The following main parameters of the population are taken into account: 1. Sex ratio. An equal ratio indicates stability. The proportion of males in 50 - 60% indicates adaptation to changing habitat conditions. The absolute predominance of males (70 - 95%) is a sign of the exhaustion of adaptive potencies. The lack of males may indicate either the most severe selection, or further adaptation of the population. It must be borne in mind that we are talking about organisms in which the normal sex ratio is 1: 1, and those are the majority. 2. Variability. Normally, for most traits, the CV coefficient of variation in most terrestrial animals is within 0.1; in aquatic animals, it can be slightly higher, up to 0.15 [11]. Exceeding this value by approximately 2 times indicates that the population is in a state of stress. Males are the first to respond to adverse conditions, the second - females. 3. Sexual dimorphism. Since males are the vanguard of evolution, traits more typical of males will spread through the population, those more typical of females will fade away. There are developed mathematical methods for the analysis of populations based on the ideology of phenogenetic indication [7].

Ecological specificity of crayfish

To apply ecological and genetic forecasting methods, it is necessary to consider the specifics of the biology of crayfish and their difference from other objects. The following circumstances must be taken into account: 1. A relatively long period of ontogenesis of cancers, 10–20 years [1]. This makes it difficult to apply the laws of large numbers to crayfish. 2. Specificity of the settlement of crayfish in the reservoir. Usually, they live in an area that is defined by a narrow strip of the area of the reservoir along the coast before the start of a sharp descent into the depths. This type of crayfish is sedentary and does not migrate far. In summer, sexually mature females and males stay in the places they have mastered, and juveniles are located closer to the coast. In this regard, the settlement model shown in Figure 2

requires clarification. The zone of initial settlement in a homogeneous environment with an equal probability of any direction of migration can have the shape of a circle. Its diameter will already exceed the strip width in the first year. In the future, at a constant migration rate, the area will grow along the trajectory in proportion to the first power of time:

$$N = K' t \quad (1)$$

In connection with these ecological features of crayfish, it is necessary to estimate the area of the coastal strip suitable for their settlement, the so-called. "useful area" of settlement for crayfish. Let's consider two extreme cases.

1. Round lakes of radius R. The area will be defined as

$$S = \pi R^2 \quad (2)$$

The area inhabited by crayfish (denoted by S_r), having a width h and separated from the coast at a distance l, is determined by the formula:

$$S_r = \pi[(R-l)^2 - (R-l-h)^2] \quad (3)$$

2. Another extreme case is an extremely elongated lake, where the width is less than 2h+l. In this case

$$S_r = S. \quad (4)$$

This situation is more characteristic of a river than a lake. However, the shape of a lake is usually not reducible to either the first or the second case. The area of the reservoir is then calculated on a case-by-case basis using a curvimeter or by cutting and weighing.

Example: settlement of lake Berezno with crayfish

Lake Berezno is in the north-west of the Pskov region, in the Gdovsky district. It is mesotrophic, has an area of 67.2 ha. A detailed description of the climatic and hydrobiological data for this reservoir is given in [2]. For the period from 1986 to 1997. about 2,000 mature crayfish *Astacus astacus* were planted in the lake, 1,000 of them are females. An analysis of the catch of crayfish in the places of their introduction made it possible to identify the following features of their distribution. In 1987 - 1988 in places of introduction into traps, crayfish were not evenly caught, even in places of their introduction. For example, trapping of crayfish in the period of August and September 1988 showed that crayfish are caught only in certain places of the lake, and not evenly along the entire perimeter along the shore, as it should have been after a uniform introduction. Spotty dispersal of crayfish after introduction along the coastline is noted in many works [2, 5]. The analysis was carried out on a coastline strip 1 km long, 50 m wide, distance from the coast. Attempts to catch crayfish in other places along the perimeter of the lake did not yield results, although during the introduction they were settled evenly along the perimeter of the lake, including on the opposite shore. The largest accumulations of crayfish were found only along one coast along the village of Glush. The trapping was carried out using standard Pirat plastic traps by Back-AS and Smalandemia reden AB. The material was processed using standard biometric methods. The average length of the cancer body in mm was calculated, the variability of the mean value was estimated through the standard deviation, the error of the mean and the coefficient of variation, the degree of sexual dimorphism, and the sex ratio.

The total number of crayfish in the lake is correlated with the size of the catch. About 800 crayfish were examined and measured. Based on the capture data, it can be assumed that the stabilization of the density of the crayfish population in the study area of the lake occurred in 1998–1999. For morphometric analysis, the dimensional characteristics of crayfish were taken. Of all the measured parameters of crayfish, the most accurate measurements relate to body length. Age classes were determined based on the well-known consideration [4] that, starting from the age of puberty (3+, 4+),

the growth of broad-clawed crayfish under natural conditions in northwestern Russia averages approximately 0.5 cm per year. According to the data of capture in 2000, the population of crayfish had the largest number of age classes – 13. In fig. Figure 3 shows the distribution of males by size and age classes in Lake Berezno based on the results of crayfish captures in August 2000. Figure 4 shows a histogram of the distribution of females by size and age categories in Lake Berezno based on the results of crayfish captures in August 1997.

Fig.3. Distribution of males by size and age categories in Lake Berezno - captures in August 2000

Analysis of figures 3 and 4 allows us to draw the following conclusions: The distribution of age classes in the population can be considered as Gaussian with asymmetry coefficient significantly different from zero. There is some asymmetry towards larger crayfish

sizes. There is an excess - a relatively small number of small crayfish and the almost complete absence of crayfish longer than 12 cm.

Fig. 4. Distribution of females by size and age categories in Lake Berezno - captures in August 1997

The lack of especially large crayfish can be explained by the following reason: they were caught more intensively and not all specimens of this category were measured. The small number of small crayfish can be explained by the fact that they either do not fall into the creels, or, having got in, crawl back through the cells. It is also known that small crayfish in the case of choosing food, as a rule, do not risk entering the creel to

larger crayfish that are already there. Table 1 shows the values of the average length, standard deviation (σ), error of the mean (M) and coefficient of variation (CV) based on the results of crayfish captures in 1997 - 2000. in Lake Berezno. Above are data of males, below are females.

Table 1

Results of the analysis of crayfish catching in Lake Berezno for 1997-2000.

year/ morphosizes	1997	1999	2000
Males – Avg. length, (mm)	112	102	105
σ	13,7	22	9,9
M	1,02	2,9	1,2
CV	0,12	0,21	0,09
Females – Avg. length, (mm)	103	101	98
σ	9,46	9,8	7
M	1,35	1,2	1,0
CV	0,09	0,097	0,07
% of males	48%	58,5	59,3

In Lake Berezno in 1999 and 2000. there was a predominance of males - according to the data of August captures, which, adjusted for the specific ecology of crayfish, can be considered representative. In October captures, the proportion of males is 86.3%. This reflects the fact that in October the females rarely fall into the creels, as after mating the females go to the shelters.

Sex ratio data demonstrate the same patterns of population dynamics as the results of the assessment of the level of variability. The coefficient of variation less than 0.1 (for aquatic organisms, the upper limit of stability is 0.15) [11] may indicate a stable population size. This is what we observed in 1997. The increase in the proportion of males in the 1999 captures coincided with

an increase in the level of variability, estimated using the coefficient of variation. As follows from the theory of dioecy [11], males are the first to respond to the deterioration of the ecological situation. Apparently, in 1998 there was a change in the physicochemical characteristics of the ecological niche of crayfish in the lake. Then the water level in the lake fell by 2 - 2.5 m

during the summer. After 1998, the stabilization of the population began. The sex ratio in subsequent years (2001 - 2005) approached 1:1. The dynamics of the number of crayfish in Lake Berezno can be assessed by the following graph - see fig. 5.

Fig.5. Dynamics of the number of crayfish in Lake Berezno.
1 - in the original site, near the village of Glush. 2 – All in all in the lake.

It can be assumed that in 1998 - 1999 there was a stabilization of the number of crayfish in the studied area of the reservoir with an area of 50,000 square meters. This follows from the data on their abundance (Table 1) and data on variability (Table 2). The cessation of the increase in the abundance of crayfish in the study area of the lake and the transition from exponential to linear dependence on time (Fig. 5) could occur during the period of over-consolidation, which gave a stimulus to the formation of a solitary wave at the boundary of the settlement area (see Fig. 2). Further growth in abundance will be carried out linearly with time according to formula (1), until the ecological capacity of the reservoir for crayfish is exhausted. The number of crayfish at the time of the beginning of settlement throughout the reservoir (N_p) can be estimated by the formula:

$$N_p = r S_b$$

where r is the density of a stable population in relatively favorable conditions. S_b is the initial area of population settlement. Based on the literature data [6], assuming $r = 0.16$ individuals per 1 m^2 of the area of the reservoir useful for crayfish, we obtain the maximum value

$$N_p = 8\,000 \text{ парков.}$$

Approximately, it is possible to estimate the rate of complete colonization of crayfish in a reservoir within the ecological capacity. The useful area of the lake based on cartographic material is estimated as S in the range from 17.9 to 18.6 ha ($186,000 \text{ m}^2$). Dividing this value by 50 meters - the width of the useful strip - we get the length = 3.7 km.

Two solitary edge waves of crayfish must each pass along half of this length and close to exhaust the assimilation capacity of the reservoir. At a speed of 1 km per year (empirical data), this could happen by 2003–2005. The number of crayfish can be $N = 186$ thousand pieces. Since crayfish reach sexual maturity at 3-4 years, a maximum capture of 25% of the entire population can be estimated. This will amount to 46.5 thousand pieces. Dividing this value by 25 (the number of commercial crayfish per 1 kg with an average length of commercial crayfish of at least 10 cm), we obtain the

number of crayfish in the lake in kilograms. This is the maximum that can be achieved for reservoirs of this type - typical for crayfish lakes, i.e. you can catch up to 1.8 tons of crayfish per year.

The greatest pressure is exerted on juvenile crayfish precisely in the summer period when insects breed [3]. The most significant factors controlling the population size of cold-water crayfish species are physicochemical: pH of the environment, oxygen saturation, the presence of Ca ions, salinity, and the substrate with the number of shelters. Among the biotic factors on which the population density of crayfish depends are the amount of food, intraspecific competition for shelters, temperature niche, and food. Interspecific competition for shelter, food, sexual partners depend on population density, as well as within, and interspecific predation. Further studies of this population of broad-toed crayfish will have to consider many issues related to the influence of intraspecific competition, as well as the influence of natural predators on the population density of crayfish in Lake Berezno. The results obtained on the formation of a single wave during the dispersal of crayfish from areas with increased density can be considered as a special case of the model of crayfish dispersal in a reservoir. Further studies should show to what extent the density of crayfish dispersal in this solitary wave can be related to the time factor of further dispersal of the population along the coastal boundary of the lake and the development of its new areas.

Conclusion

The existing groundwork in the field of population genetics and ecology, methods of applied mathematics make it possible to model the process of the spread of crayfish in a reservoir after introduction, considering the assimilation capacity and make predictions with a greater or lesser degree of probability. There are two types of ecological models - dynamic and static. Dynamic ones are based on long-term observations of ecological processes and extrapolation of their results into the future. Statistics are based on one-time observations and detection of developmental trends based on the analysis of the population at a given point in time. The

most important of these methods is the method of phenogenetic indication. When making forecasts of the spread of cancers, an integrated approach that combines statistical and dynamic methods may be most fruitful.

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